

</p> <p>The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States</p>		
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Data set of measurement data vs test conditions for IT performance characterised in the presence of separate and combined influence factors, including concise description of measurement data and test conditions.

Grant Agreement number: **19NRM05**

Project short name: IT5PQ

Project full title: **Measurement methods and test procedures for assessing accuracy of instrument transformers in power quality measurements**

List of dataset content, provided by each partner:

- UNIBO: effect of temperature and humidity
- INRIM: effect of conductor position and adjacent phases
- LNE: effect of temperature, vibration and harmonics
- PTB: effect of adjacent phases and conductor position
- TUBITAK: effect of current on VT and of voltage on CT
- TUD: effect of temperature and burden

Dataset structure:

Each partner provided:

- One or more compressed files (.zip or .rar) containing the raw data. These [last](#) files are named 19NRM05_datasetname_partername.zip (or .rar)
- the related pdf files containing an explanation of what enclosed in the compressed files. The pdf are named 19NRM05_datasetname_partername_description.pdf.

Lead partner: **UNIBO**

Partners involved: INRIM, LNE, PTB, TUBITAK, TUD

Contributors

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